

Search for New Oral Hypoglycemic Agents. Part VI

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Several substituted thiazolyhydantoin and -thiohydantoin have been prepared for testing their hypoglycemic activity.

After the discovery of 2-isopropyl-5-sulphanilylthiodiazole (IPTD, VK 57 or RP 2254) as a hypoglycemic agent by Janbon¹, thiodiazoles have been extensively studied² and several of them have been found to possess marked hypoglycemic activity. Recently Holan *et al.*⁶ prepared many 3-alkyl- and 1-aryl-sulphonylhydantoin, which showed marked hypoglycemic activity.

Keeping in view the observations of these workers, we have prepared several *N*¹-(4-alkylthiazole-2-yl) and *N*³-arylsulphonyl-hydantoin and -thiohydantoin (*I*: R=H, Cl, Me, and OMe) which are reported in the present communication.

2-Amino-4-alkylthiazoles were prepared by condensing the appropriate ketones with thiourea. *N*¹-(4-alkylthiazolyl-2)-ureas and -thioureas were prepared by the condensation of amine hydrochloride and urea or thiourea in water. *N*¹-(4-Alkylthiazole-2-yl)-hydantoin and -2-thiohydantoin were prepared by the condensation of substituted thiazolyureas or -thioureas (thiazolyurea, thiazolythiourea, 4-methylthiazolyurea, 4-methylthiazolythiourea) with monochloroacetic acid separately in anhydrous pyridine. Finally, these

1. *Montpellier. Med.*, 1942, 21, 441.
2. Loubatieres, *Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1944, 138, 830.
3. Davis *et al.*, *Canad. Med. Assoc. J.*, 1959, 81, 101.
4. Kuranari, *Nippon Naibunpi Gakkai Zasshi*, 1959, 3, 67.
5. Healy and Arneaud, *Brit. Med. J.*, 1960, 2, 913.
6. Holan and Samuel, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 4860.

hydantoins and thiohydantoins were condensed with different arylsulphonyl chlorides. The m.p., yields, and analyses etc. of the compounds are reported in Table I.

TABLE I

Sl. No.	R.	R'.	M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Reqd.
1	H	..	171°	70	C ₆ H ₅ ON ₃ S	29.12	29.37
2	Me	..	141°	76	C ₇ H ₇ ON ₃ S	26.60	26.75
3	H	-	101°	75	C ₄ H ₅ N ₃ S ₂	26.10	26.40
4	Me	-	154°	72	C ₅ H ₇ N ₃ S ₂	24.10	24.30
5	H	..	148°	63	C ₆ H ₅ O ₂ N ₃ S	22.82	22.94
6	Me	..	132°	67	C ₇ H ₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	21.23	21.31
7	H	..	No melting	70	C ₆ H ₅ ON ₃ S ₂	19.90	21.10
8	Me	..	154°	72	C ₇ H ₇ ON ₃ S ₂	19.63	19.71
9	H	H	> 250°	52	C ₁₆ H ₉ O ₄ N ₃ S ₂	12.90	13.00
10	H	Me	> 250°	54	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃ S ₂	12.38	12.50

TABLE I (contd.)

Sl. No.	R.	R'.	M.P.	%Yield.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Reqd
11	H	OMe	122°	60	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃ S ₂	11.76	11.90
12	H	Cl	132°	48	C ₁₂ H ₈ O ₄ N ₃ ClS ₂	11.56	11.87
13	Me	H	> 250°	56	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃ S ₂	12.34	12.46
14	..	Me	> 250°	52	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃ S ₂	11.92	11.96
15	..	OMe	128°	62	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃ S ₂	11.38	11.44
16	..	Cl	148°	50	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₃ ClS ₂	11.30	11.32

17	H	H	> 250°	60	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₃ N ₃ S ₃	12.32	12.39
18	H	Me	> 250°	55	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃ S ₃	11.72	11.90
19	H	OMe	112°	58	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃ S ₃	11.32	11.38
20	H	Cl	158°	56	C ₁₂ H ₈ O ₃ N ₃ ClS ₃	11.23	11.26
21	Me	H	> 250°	62	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃ S ₃	11.80	11.90
22	..	Me	> 250°	60	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃ S ₃	11.31	11.41
23	..	OMe	70°	52	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃ S ₃	10.92	10.96
24	..	Cl	192°	54	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₃ ClS ₃	10.30	10.32

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Amino-4-alkylthiazoles were prepared by heating urea or thiourea (0.1M), iodine (0.05M), and the appropriate ketone (0.2M), following the method of Dodson and King⁷.

N¹-(4-Alkylthiazolyl-2)-ureas.—A mixture of the hydrochloride of 2-amino-4-alkylthiazole (0.1M) and urea (0.1M) in water (100 ml), containing HCl (0.1 ml) and glacial acetic acid (0.5 ml), was refluxed for 4 hours. The substituted urea separating on cooling was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

N¹-(4-Alkylthiazolyl-2)-thioureas—A mixture of thiourea (0.1M) and hydrochloride of 2-amino-4-alkylthiazole (0.1M) in water (100 ml), containing HCl (0.1ml) and glacial acetic acid (0.5 ml), was refluxed for 4 hours. On cooling the mixture, the corresponding thioureas separated, which were recrystallised from ethanol.

N¹-(4-Alkylthiazole-2-yl)-hydantoin.—4-Alkylthiazole-2-urea (0.1M) and monochloroacetic acid (0.1M) were taken in anhydrous pyridine (50 ml) and the mixture was warmed on a water bath. On completion of the reaction, it was cooled when a viscous material was obtained. Absolute ethanol was added to it and the mixture refluxed under anhydrous condition. A crystalline substance was obtained, which was recrystallised from methanol.

N¹-(4-Alkylthiazole-2-yl)-2-thiohydantoin.—A mixture of 4-alkylthiazole-2-thiourea (0.1M) and monochloroacetic acid (0.1M) were taken in anhydrous pyridine (50 ml) and

warmed on a water bath, when an exothermic reaction took place. After the reaction was over, absolute ethanol was added and the mixture refluxed. A crystalline substance separated, which was recrystallised from methanol.

*N*¹-(4-Alkylthiazole-2-yl)-*N*³-arylsulphonylhydantion.—A mixture of arylsulphonyl chloride (0.05*M*), the appropriate hydantion (0.25*M*) in ethanol (10 ml), and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.25*M*) was refluxed under anhydrous condition on a water bath for 4 hours. It was filtered hot. The filtrate on cooling deposited a crystalline compound, which was recrystallised from hot absolute ethanol.

*N*¹-(4-Alkylthiazole-2-yl)-*N*³-arylsulphonyl-2-thiohydantoin.—Arylsulphonyl chloride (0.05*M*) was refluxed with the appropriate thiohydantoin (0.025*M*) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.25*M*) in absolute ethanol for 3 hours. The resulting thiohydantions were isolated as described above.

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